

STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS OF NOUNS IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES

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Abstract: In this article, we will explore the structural analysis of nouns in Uzbek and English, two languages that are spoken in different parts of the world and have distinct features.

Keywords: nouns, structural analysis, Uzbek language, English language, gender, case, number, possessive, plural, proper nouns, collective nouns.

Languages are a fundamental aspect of human culture and communication. They allow us to express ourselves, convey information, and understand the world around us. Each language has its own unique set of rules and structures that govern its use, including its grammar, syntax, and vocabulary. One important aspect of language is its system of nouns, which are words that refer to people, places, things, and ideas.

Uzbek Language. Uzbek is a Turkic language that is spoken primarily in Uzbekistan, as well as in parts of Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Afghanistan, and Turkey. It is the official language of Uzbekistan and has over 30 million speakers worldwide. Uzbek is written in the Latin script, although it was previously written in the Cyrillic and Arabic scripts. Nouns in Uzbek are generally classified into two categories: common nouns and proper nouns. Common nouns refer to generic objects, while proper nouns refer to specific objects or individuals.

Uzbek nouns do not have gender or case, but they do have number and possessive forms.

Number. In Uzbek, nouns have two number forms: singular and plural. The plural form is usually formed by adding the suffix *-lar* or *-lar/er* to the end of the noun. For example, the word "kitob" means "book" in singular form, while "kitoblar" means "books" in plural form. However, there are some irregular plural forms that do not follow this pattern, such as the word "odam" (man), which becomes "odamlar" in plural form.

Possessive. Uzbek nouns also have a possessive form, which is formed by adding the suffix *-ning* to the end of the noun. This indicates possession, and is used to show that the noun belongs to someone or something. For example, the word "kitob" (book) becomes "kitobning" (book's) in possessive form.

Proper Nouns. Proper nouns in Uzbek refer to specific individuals, places, or things. They are capitalized in writing and do not take any suffixes for number or possession. For example, the name "Toshkent" (Tashkent) is a proper noun in Uzbek, and it is not affected by number or possession.

English Language. English is a West Germanic language that is spoken worldwide, with over 1.5 billion speakers. It is the official language of many countries, including the United Kingdom, the United States, Australia, Canada, and New Zealand. English is written in the Latin script and has a complex system of grammar, syntax, and vocabulary. Nouns in English are classified into several categories, including common nouns, proper nouns, abstract nouns, and collective nouns. English nouns have several grammatical features, including gender, number, case, and possessive form.

Gender. English nouns have two genders: masculine and feminine. This gender system is not based on biological sex, but on grammatical convention. For example, the word "boy" is masculine, while the word "girl" is feminine. However, there are many nouns in English that are gender-neutral, such as "book," "car," or "table."

Number. In English, nouns have two number forms: singular and plural. The plural form is usually formed by adding the suffix -s or -es to the end of the noun. For example, the word "book" becomes "books" in plural form. However, there are some irregular plural forms that do not follow this pattern, such as the word "child" (children) or "foot".

Possessive. English nouns also have a possessive form, which is formed by adding an apostrophe and an "s" to the end of the noun. This indicates possession, and is used to show that the noun belongs to someone or something. For example, the phrase "the book of John" becomes "John's book" in possessive form.

Case. English nouns have three cases: nominative, objective, and possessive. The nominative case is used for the subject of a sentence, while the objective case is used for the object of a sentence. The possessive case is used to indicate possession, as described above. However, the distinction between nominative and objective case is not always visible in modern English, as the same form is often used for both.

Structural Comparison of Nouns in Uzbek and English. There are several notable differences between the structural analysis of nouns in Uzbek and English. One of the most significant differences is the absence of gender and case in Uzbek nouns. In English, nouns have two genders and three cases, which can affect their form and function in a sentence. However, Uzbek nouns have number and possessive forms, which are not present in all English nouns. Another difference is the formation of plural nouns. In Uzbek, plural nouns are usually formed by adding the suffix -lar or -lar/er to the end of the noun, while in English, plural nouns are usually formed by adding the suffix -s or -es to the end of the noun. Additionally, English has several irregular plural forms that do not follow this pattern, while Uzbek has a smaller number of irregular plural forms. Finally, there are some differences in the use of proper nouns and collective nouns in Uzbek and English. In English, proper nouns are capitalized and do not take any suffixes for number or possession, while in Uzbek, proper nouns are not capitalized but are treated the

same as common nouns in terms of number and possession. In terms of collective nouns, English has a more complex system of treating them as either singular or plural, while in Uzbek, collective nouns are always treated as plural.

REFERENCES

1. Türker, L. (2019). Noun phrases in article-less languages: Uzbek and beyond (Vol. 253). John Benjamins Publishing Company.
2. Usmanova, S. (2022). Comparative analysis of landscape terms in Uzbek and English and usage of terms. *Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching*, 14, 1-3.
3. Rikhsivayevna, S. B. (2021). Structural And Semantic Aspects of Lexemic Units Expressing National Value in English and Uzbek Languages. *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 2, 37-39.
4. Alisherovna, M. B. (2020). Comparative analysis of the English and Russian proverbs and sayings representating the concept "money". *Проблемы современной науки и образования*, (4-2 (149)), 43-45.
4. qizi Usmonova, U. H., & Mukhtorova, B. (2023). PAREMIOLOGICAL UNITS OF LANGUAGE. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 1(1), 241-244.
5. Абдуразакова, Ш., & Мухторова, Б. (2023). ЛИНГВИСТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ТЕКСТА. *Scientific progress*, 4(1), 369-373.
6. Mukhtorova, B. (2023). THE LINGUISTIC AND CONCEPTUAL PICTURE OF THE WORLD. *Science and innovation*, 2(B1), 461-466.
7. Мухторова, Б. А. (2022, September). МОДАЛЛИК КАТЕГОРИЯСИНИНГ ЛИСОНИЙ ҲАМДА МАНТИҚИЙ ТАДҚИҚИ. In *INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE "THE TIME OF SCIENTIFIC PROGRESS"* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 55-61).